

FLOODPLAIN LIKE A SPONGE

TEACHING PROTOCOL

TYPE OF LESSON: Workshop

GRADE LEVEL: Secondary school

LESSON STRUCTURE: 90 minutes (30 minutes introduction, 60 minutes activity and 30 minutes conclusions)

The workshop can be done outside, but some infrastructure is necessary – e.g. benches or wooden tables

INTRODUCTION:

This lesson helps students understand the vital role natural river floodplains play in reducing the impact of heavy rainfall. With diverse soils and vegetation, natural floodplains slow and absorb excess water, preventing rapid runoff into nearby communities and lowering flood risk. In contrast, artificial river channels made of concrete lack the permeability and irregular structure of natural floodplains. Their smooth and rigid surfaces speed up water flow without any absorption, significantly increasing runoff velocity. This rapid flow heightens the risk of flooding in urban areas, as water is unable to disperse or infiltrate the ground. Urban development often involves replacing natural floodplains with concrete infrastructure, leading to the loss of an essential natural buffer. Without these floodplains, cities face greater challenges in managing floodwaters, resulting in increased flood severity and heightened risks to communities.

KEYWORDS: floodplain, flood risk, artificial river channels, natural flood management

LEARNING OBJECTIVES:

By the end of this lesson, students will be able to:

- 1 Explain how natural river floodplains act like sponges, absorbing and storing excess water during heavy rains.
- 2 Identify the key features of floodplains that help slow down and absorb water. Describe the impact of artificial river channels made of concrete on water flow and flooding risks in urban areas.
- 3 Understand the consequences of replacing natural floodplains with concrete channels and the resulting increase in flood hazards.
- 4 Discuss the importance of preserving natural floodplains as a safety measure for flood management in cities.

TEACHING FRAMEWORK BASED ON THE 5E INSTRUCTIONAL MODEL

1. ENGAGE - Sparking curiosity

AIM: Capture interest and activate prior knowledge about flood management

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Have you ever witnessed flood?
- Have you ever seen how natural landscapes deal with heavy rains compared to cities?
- How do you think nature manages floods?

ACTIVITIES:

1 DISCUSSION

Teacher facilitates a discussion with listed question

2 DEMONSTRATION

1. Teacher pours water onto two sponges — one clean and the other encased in plastic wrap — to hint at the difference between natural floodplains and urbanized areas.

2. Divide the class students into two main groups: **Group A – WATER DROPS** and **Group B – GROUND PARTICLES**

- **Group A – WATER DROPS:**

This group represents drops of water moving through the substrate in both exercises. They should try to pass through the “ground particles”, moving between the lines of students (Group B).

- **Group B – GROUND PARTICLES**

Arrange two parallel lines of students facing each other.

1ST EXERCISE - when representing soil: students stand loosely spaced apart, leaving small gaps between them. A few students can stand between the two lines to represent plant roots.

2ND EXERCISE - when representing concrete: students stand very close together, holding hands tightly to form a dense barrier.

OBSERVATION AND DISCUSSION:

- When the “water drops” pass through loosely spaced soil, they can move easily — this shows that soil is porous.
- When they try to pass through tightly packed concrete, they cannot — this shows that concrete is non-porous.
- Compare this to a sponge demonstration: water passes through the sponge (porous) but not through a solid block (non-porous).

To continue the discussion, the teacher poses a question:

“Imagine a world without wetlands. What do you think would happen during a storm?”

3 ENGAGING CURIOSITY WITH EXAMPLES

Teacher shows an engaging video clip or images comparing a flooded urban area vs a healthy floodplain during heavy rain (links are available on Youtube; photographs are available on free web sites e.g. <https://www.istockphoto.com/>)

2. EXPLORE – Hands-on learning activity

AIM: To conduct a hands-on investigation to develop an understanding of water flow dynamics and the role of natural versus artificial features.

ACTIVITIES:

1 MODEL CONSTRUCTION:

Following the procedure (see [worksheet](#)), each student will construct two table-top models:

1. River with adjacent floodplains.
2. Artificial river channel.

2 SIMULATING RAINFALL:

Once both models are completed, students will simulate rainfall and flood by pouring water from bottles over the models and into the “river channel”.

3 OBSERVATION AND ANALYSIS:

Students will observe and compare the differences in water absorption, runoff, and flow velocity between the two models.

3. EXPLAIN – Making sense of the experiences

AIM: Help students articulate their understanding and clarify concepts.

ACTIVITIES:

1 DISCUSSION

Teacher facilitate a discussion by asking guiding questions:

- “Why did the natural floodplain absorb more water?”
- “How do plants and soil slow water flow?”
- “What happens to water in areas without floodplains?”

2 STUDENTS FILL OUT THE QUESTIONNAIRE TO SUMMARIZE THE OUTCOMES OF THE DISCUSSION.

Instructions for students:

1. Read the question: Ensure you fully understand each question in the table. The focus is on the comparison of rainfall absorption.
2. Column completion: Provide a detailed and precise response for each column:
 - A river with adjacent floodplains: Describe the natural processes, structures, and characteristics that affect rainfall absorption.
 - An artificial river channel: Explain how its design and materials influence rainfall absorption and runoff.
3. Detail-oriented: Include key factors such as:
 - Soil and substrate characteristics.
 - Influence of vegetation.

4. EXTEND / ELABORATE – Expanding understanding

AIM: Extend learning by applying knowledge to new, real-world scenarios.

ACTIVITIES:

1 SCENARIO-BASED GROUP ACTIVITY:

Teacher divides students into two groups and assigns real-world challenges: urban development near rivers and deforestation.

By searching examples using internet sources, students design a floodplain restoration plan addressing these issues, incorporating:

- Replanting vegetation
- Restoring wetlands
- Creating buffer zones

Each plan must explain the biological mechanisms and benefits of their approach.

2 GROUP PRESENTATIONS:

Groups present their plans, focusing on how their solutions use biological principles to reduce flooding and support biodiversity.

5. EVALUATE – Assessing learning

AIM: Assess understanding and encourage reflection.

ACTIVITY:

PUB QUIZ – “FLOODPLAIN LIKE A SPONGE”

- Teacher divides the class into small groups.
- One group is tasked with designing a pub quiz using the free online tool Canva (<https://www.canva.com/>). The quiz questions should be based on the questionnaire that students completed earlier in the class.
- Quiz competition: The remaining groups compete in answering the quiz questions to earn points. Each correct answer is worth one point. The time limit for answering each question is 30 seconds.
- Objective: The group with the highest score at the end of the quiz wins.

AUTHORS: Alma Mikuška, Dubravka Čerba - Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek (UNIOS)

FLOODPLAIN LIKE A SPONGE

WORKSHEET

PROCEDURE FOR BUILDING TABLE-TOP MODELS

MATERIALS NEEDED:

- two aluminium baking trays (dimension at least: 50x30x10 cm)
- sand
- soil
- gravel
- spoon for modelling gravel, soil, sand and clay
- vegetation (small grass with roots and moss)
- small branches
- modelling clay
- model houses - toys
- bottle with water
- clean-up supplies (paper towels, sponges, towels, etc.)

- 1 Take one aluminium baking tray and put on the bottom soil, gravel and sand. Build a riverbed from one to other side of the baking tray. On the banks of the riverbed add moss and vegetation. Spread vegetation on both sides of the river (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Table-top model of natural river with adjacent floodplain

- 2 Take another aluminium baking tray and put on the bottom soil, gravel sand and vegetation. Put model houses. In this model make riverbed from one to other side of the baking tray with modelling clay. Modelling clay simulates concrete riverbed (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Table-top model of artificial river channel

- 3 Make a combination of the natural and artificial channels/habitats.
- 4 Simulate rainfall/flood by pouring water from bottles over the models. Observe differences between the models.
- 5 Clean working surface. Table-top models can be stored for other classes as examples.

AUTHORS: Alma Mikuška, Dubravka Čerba - Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek (UNIOS)

Illustrator: Anca Smărăndache

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WORKSHEET

QUESTIONNAIRE TO SUMMARIZE THE OUTCOMES OF THE DISCUSSION

To complete questionnaire and clarify the differences in rainfall absorption between a river with adjacent floodplains and an artificial river channel, see examples in the table and follow these instructions:

- 1 READ THE QUESTION:** Ensure you fully understand each question in the table. The focus is on the comparison of rainfall absorption.
- 2 COLUMN COMPLETION:** Provide a detailed and precise response for each column:
 - A river with adjacent floodplains: Describe the natural processes, structures, and characteristics that affect rainfall absorption.
 - An artificial river channel: Explain how its design and materials influence rainfall absorption and runoff.
- 3 DETAIL-ORIENTED:** Include key factors such as:
 - Soil and substrate characteristics.
 - Influence of vegetation.
 - Floodwater distribution and storage.
 - Impact on local ecosystems.

Question	A river with adjacent floodplains	An artificial river channel
Rainfall absorption mechanisms	High due to porous soil and vegetation absorption.	Low due to impermeable channel lining.
Floodwater storage		
Impact on groundwater recharge		
Erosion control		
Biodiversity support		
Response to heavy rainfall events		
Water quality improvement		
Maintenance requirements		

FLOODPLAIN LIKE A SPONGE

WORKSHEET

QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS TO SUMMARIZE THE OUTCOMES OF THE DISCUSSION

Question	A river with adjacent floodplains	An artificial river channel
Rainfall absorption mechanisms	High due to porous soil and vegetation absorption.	Low due to impermeable channel lining.
Floodwater storage	Spreads across floodplains, reducing peak flow.	Limited storage; rapid runoff downstream.
Impact on groundwater recharge	Promotes significant recharge through infiltration.	Minimal recharge due to low permeability.
Erosion control	Natural vegetation and slower flow reduce erosion.	High flow velocity increases erosion risk.
Biodiversity support	Provides diverse habitats for flora and fauna.	Limited habitat availability; often degraded.
Response to heavy rainfall events	Absorbs and distributes water, mitigating flooding.	Channels water quickly, increasing flood risk downstream.
Water quality improvement	Filters pollutants through soil and vegetation.	Limited filtration: runoff may carry pollutants.